

Development and Validation of an Interactive Learning Module in Grade 8 Earth Science

Rich Paulo S. Lim

*School of Education, Arts, and Sciences, Faculty,
National University Philippines, Philippines*

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Abstract:

This study was a Research and Development (R&D) Design. It is concerned with the development and validation of an Interactive Learning Earth Science module based on the Kto12 curriculum of grade 8. Two groups were selected from the heterogeneous sections of Grade 8 in Atlu-Bola High School during the school year 2023 – 2024. They were used in this study as subjects. They were randomly arranged into experimental and control groups. Traditional, or discussion methods were used in both the experimental group and the control group. The only difference was that the experimental

group was exposed with the use of the developed module. The t – test was used to determine whether there would be a difference between the scores of the control and experimental groups in the pre-test and post-test. It was found that the students in the experimental group performed better than the traditional method. This implies that the interactive learning module was effective in teaching Earth Science. The results of this study clearly show that the developed module is a tool in increasing students' academic performance. This study may be adopted by other teachers in the field to improve their teaching methodology. This module also suits the way of learning of the 21st century learners. This study would support interactive instructional material in teaching Science inside the classroom.

Keywords: *Interactive Learning Module, Development and Validation, Science Curriculum, Earth Science, K-12.*

Introduction

At the heart of a thorough understanding of 21st-century teaching and learning is the integration of modern student achievements, specific skills, knowledge, expertise, and literacies—with cutting-edge support systems meant to help students acquire the variety of skills that will be expected of them in the future (Pacific Policy Research Center, 2010). Modern scientific curricula should aim to provide students with access to a support system that will enable them to gain 21st-century skills, according to the Center for 21st Century Skills (2014). The development of scientific literacy

and the encouragement of an understanding of the nature of science and its societal significance should precede over topic knowledge in science education, according to the Office of the Prime Minister's Science Advisory Committee (2011).

One noteworthy feature of the Philippine K–12 Curriculum is the incorporation of contextualization and enrichment. The Philippine educational system is becoming less and less effective, and the Department of Education (DepEd) sees K–12 education as a workable solution (Oteyza, 2012). It also recognizes the burden of the ten-year

curriculum, which forces pupils to absorb a lot of information and abilities in a short amount of time (Oteyza, 2012). The K–12 framework places a high priority on integrative education to provide kids with the life skills they require, encourage critical and creative thinking, and prepare them for the workforce (Velasco, 2012). Luistro claims that the first year of the high school curriculum is more practical and relevant to real-world situations, especially in the science department where real-world scenarios are heavily stressed. In order to ensure that students find satisfaction and appreciation in their classes, he highlights the necessity of matching educational content with industrial expectations (Velasco, 2012). DepEd gives special attention to the fields of science and mathematics.

Unfortunately, teacher-centered instruction is still widely employed in Philippine schools. Rather than assigning their students difficult, thought-provoking assignments, many scientific teachers would rather lecture since they lack the pedagogical experience and subject-matter expertise that is required. Students' general impression of science as boring and useless is exacerbated by the fact that scientific education frequently depends too heavily on textbooks and fails to make connections between concepts and community contexts or real-world situations.

The performance of Filipino students in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) has raised significant concerns regarding the effectiveness of the science curriculum in the Philippines. In the 2018 PISA results, Filipino students ranked near the bottom among 79 countries, scoring an average of 357 in science, which is substantially lower than the OECD average of 489 Dollete (2021). This alarming performance has prompted educators and policymakers to examine the underlying issues within the science curriculum and its implementation in the K-12 education system.

One of the critical problems identified is the structure of the K-12 science curriculum itself. The curriculum employs a spiral progression approach, where students revisit topics with increasing complexity throughout their education (Antipolo & Rogayan, 2021).

However, many prospective science teachers have reported challenges in effectively delivering this curriculum, indicating a disconnect between curriculum design and classroom practice (Antipolo & Rogayan, 2021). Furthermore, the curriculum's focus on rote memorization rather than inquiry-based learning has been criticized, as it does not adequately prepare students for the type of critical thinking and problem-solving skills necessary for scientific literacy (Sjøberg, 2018).

Additionally, the integration of environmental education and sustainability concepts into the science curriculum has been insufficient. Maimad emphasizes the need for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) to be mainstreamed within the science curriculum, particularly in areas such as environmental education and disaster risk reduction (Maimad, 2023). This lack of integration limits students' ability to apply scientific knowledge to real-world problems, which is essential for fostering scientific literacy and engagement.

Moreover, the socio-economic context of students plays a significant role in their academic performance. Studies have shown that students from lower socio-economic backgrounds tend to perform worse in science assessments, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to support these learners (Bernardo, 2020). The PISA results reflect this disparity, as they indicate that socio-economic status moderates the relationship between students' mindsets and their performance in mathematics and science (Bernardo, 2020).

The challenges faced by the Philippine science curriculum are compounded by the broader educational environment, which has been criticized for its lack of resources and support for teachers. Cordova and Linaugo point out that the professional development of science teachers is crucial for improving pedagogical content knowledge and, consequently, student outcomes (Cordova & Linaugo, 2022). Without adequate training and resources, teachers may struggle to implement effective teaching strategies that promote scientific inquiry and critical thinking.

The PISA results underscore the urgent need for reform in the Philippine science curriculum. Addressing the structural issues within the curriculum, enhancing teacher training, integrating sustainability education, and considering the socio-economic factors affecting student performance are essential steps toward improving science education in the Philippines. By focusing on these areas, the country can work towards elevating its students' scientific literacy and overall educational outcomes.

The National Achievement Test results for the Mabalacat Division for the 2020–2021 school year showed a wide variation in scores throughout the 13 secondary schools, ranging from 37.72 to 50.24, indicating a significant amount of space for growth. For example, in the 2023–2024 academic year, Atlu–Bola High School obtained the lowest Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of any school for science courses in Grade 8 Science—56.31.

According to Yaron et al. (2010), junior high school students find it challenging to understand many scientific concepts, particularly in Earth Science, due to a lack of textbooks. These ideas are purely theoretical. Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are therefore now viewed by many educators as a useful instrument for science instruction in the classroom. These technologies enable the creation of educational resources that help students understand scientific ideas. Baumert and Kunter (2016) stress the importance of instructional strategies in the teaching and learning process as well as the need for educators to stay current with new developments in the field to enhance the educational experiences of their students.

The integration of interactive learning modules in science education is increasingly recognized as essential for enhancing student engagement and understanding. Research indicates that interactive learning environments, particularly those that incorporate technology, can significantly improve science learning outcomes. For instance, Mulvey et al. highlight that experiences in high-quality informal learning environments correlate with growth in scientific

reasoning and overall science learning outcomes, suggesting that interactive experiences are vital for effective learning in science contexts (Mulvey et al., 2020). Similarly, Liu and Schunn emphasize that out-of-school science experiences provide students with additional opportunities to engage with scientific phenomena, positively influencing their science knowledge and attitudes (Liu & Schunn, 2018).

The constructivist learning theory, which underpins many interactive learning approaches, posits that knowledge is constructed through social interaction and experiential learning (Nuraeni, 2023). This theory supports the notion that interactive modules can facilitate deeper understanding by allowing students to engage actively with content rather than passively receiving information. Furthermore, Saltan et al. argue that integrating educational technologies into science education enhances students' capabilities and makes lessons more engaging and comprehensible (Saltan et al., 2018). This aligns with the findings of Tsivitanidou and Ioannou, who note that formative assessments, when implemented interactively, can lead to improved learning outcomes in science education (Tsivitanidou & Ioannou, 2019).

Moreover, the importance of fostering interest in science through interactive learning is underscored by Dabney et al., who assert that engaging students in novel and relevant situations can cultivate long-term interest in STEM fields (Dabney et al., 2012). This is particularly crucial given the observed decline in students' interest in science, as noted by Nishimura et al., who link this trend to educational policies that fail to connect science learning with students' daily lives (Nishimura et al., 2021). Therefore, interactive learning modules that relate scientific concepts to real-world applications can help mitigate this decline and foster a more positive attitude toward science.

In addition, the integration of interactive technologies in science education is supported by the findings of Kuang, who emphasizes the role of digital tools in enhancing foundational science education experiences (Kuang, 2023).

These tools not only facilitate engagement but also prepare students for future scientific endeavors by developing critical skills necessary for navigating a technology-driven world. Furthermore, the adoption of integrated STEM approaches, as discussed by Asunda, highlights the need for students to engage in authentic problem-solving processes, which can be effectively achieved through interactive learning modules (Asunda, 2023).

The need for interactive learning modules in science education is underscored by a wealth of research demonstrating their effectiveness in enhancing engagement, understanding, and interest in science. By leveraging technology and constructivist principles, these modules can provide students with meaningful learning experiences that connect scientific concepts to their everyday lives, ultimately fostering a more robust and enduring interest in the sciences.

An interactive Earth Science learning module was developed as part of a study at Atlu-Bola High Academy in Mabalacat City Division for the 2023–2024 academic year in order to make scientific concepts easier to understand.

Research Objectives

This project aimed to develop and test an interactive Earth Science learning module for eighth-grade K–12 students. During the 2023–2024 academic year, the research was carried out at Mabalacat City's Atlu–Bola High School.

Specifically, this study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. To develop an interactive learning module in Earth Science
2. To validate the module by
 - 2.1 evaluation of the Science experts in terms of:
 - 2.1.1 content
 - 2.1.2 adequacy of the scope
 - 2.1.3 language and presentation
 - 2.2 evaluation of the Information Technology (IT) experts in terms of:
 - 2.2.1 usability;
 - 2.2.2 functionality; and

2.2.3 user interface

2.3 effectiveness to users

3. To derive implications to Science education.

Method

To develop and evaluate an interactive Earth Science learning module that complies with the K–12 curriculum for eighth-grade students, the project used a research and development (R&D) design. Phases of planning, development, and validation made up this process.

First, the courses were chosen using the Department of Education's Grade 8 Earth Science Curriculum Guide, with an emphasis on understanding typhoons, earthquakes and faults, and other solar system components. Experts in information and technology offered suggestions for the module's structure, appearance, and design.

After the curriculum was created and approved, student evaluations were used to gauge its efficacy. A pretest-posttest control method was employed to assess its influence on the learning objectives.

In the academic year 2023-2024, sixty (60) students from Atlu-Bola High School in Pampanga participated in the study. Equal numbers of thirty kids from various backgrounds were split between St. Mary and St. Bernadette divisions. After then, the class was split up into two groups: the experimental group and the control group. Conventional or discussion-based teaching methods were used to instruct both groups; the experimental group also had access to the newly built interactive learning module.

The first performance of each group was evaluated using the pretest. The t-test for independent and correlated data was used to compare the mean scores between the two groups at a significance level of 0.05 in order to find any significant variations in performance.

Pre- and post-tests were the main tools used in the study to evaluate the modules' efficacy on various Earth Science themes. Furthermore, the

module was validated using a checklist that Laxamana (2012) amended after Samson (2007) designed it. The checklist addressed three crucial criteria: substance, acceptable scope, and language and presentation. This validation tool was utilized by scientific education specialists and IT professionals to evaluate the module's relevance and functionality, respectively.

An examination of the pretest and posttest scores from the experimental and control groups provided additional evidence of the module's efficacy. To search for any significant differences, the scores were totaled, compared, and added together. A significance threshold of 0.05 was applied.

The validation of the learning modules, which were based on specific Earth Science subjects, marked the start of the study and data collection procedure. The primary objective was to compile preliminary evaluations of the suggested Earth Science module material. For recommendations and ideas on how to improve and streamline the modules, panelists and advisors were contacted. Five (5) experts in

Earth Science education then assessed the materials, focusing on their appropriate presentation, language, content, and scope. Additionally, three (3) information technology (IT) specialists assessed the interactive learning module's usability, functionality, and user interface. In order to ascertain the effectiveness of the module, sixty (60) Grade 8 students from Atlu-Bola High School took part in an interactive learning

Result

Validation of the Interactive Learning Module in Earth Science by Science Experts

Research and development methods were used in the creation of the Earth Science interactive learning module. The initial step in identifying learning skills for Earth Science themes was to undertake research using the DepEd Grade 8 K–12 Curriculum Guide. This lesson covers topics such as Understanding Typhoons, Earthquakes and Faults, and Other Elements of the Solar System.

Table 1. Evaluation of Science Experts

Criteria	Science Experts					Total	Mean	Description
	1	2	3	4	5			
Content	5	5	5	5	5	25	5	Excellent
Adequacy of Scope	5	5	4.6	4.8	4.8	24.2	4.84	Excellent
Language and Presentation	5	4.8	5	5	5	24.8	4.96	Excellent
	Total Mean						4.93	Excellent

Table 1 shows that science professionals highly esteem the interactive learning module and it is valid. The grand mean of the assessment that these specialists finished is 4.93. According to the science experts, the module is deemed "highly acceptable," meaning that eighth-grade pupils can use it with great success.

Validation of the Interactive Learning Module in Earth Science by IT Experts

The Earth Science interactive learning module was evaluated by three IT specialists who offered comments on its usability, functionality, and user interface. The IT experts gave the module outstanding ratings for usability (4.78), functionality (5.0), and user interface (4.89), as indicated in Table 2. With a grand mean score of 4.89, the module was evaluated exceptionally well. This simply indicates that the curriculum is highly recommended for IT experts.

Table 2. Evaluation of IT Experts

Criteria	Science Experts			Total	Mean	Description
	1	2	3			
Validating for Usability	5	4.67	4.67	14.34	4.78	Excellent
Validating for Functionality	5	5	5	15	5	Excellent
Validating for User Interface	5	4.67	5	14.67	4.89	Excellent
	Total Mean				4.89	Excellent

Validation of the Interactive Learning Module by Students

By utilizing the t-test statistical approach to compare the pretest and posttest results between the control and experimental groups, the built interactive learning module was verified. Each group's pretest and posttest data were noted, totaled, and their corresponding means or averages were examined at a significance level of 0.05.

The results show that the interactive learning module performed significantly better than the standard module, as Table 3 shows. There was a discernible difference between the two groups' performances. More precisely, the experimental group's mean score was much higher—14.03—than the control group's (6.23). The interactive learning module is significantly more effective in teaching Earth Science than the conventional method, as evidenced by the difference of 7.8 points. Using the designed module appears to have improved the students' performance.

Table 3. Comparison of the Control and Experimental Groups' Mean Scores

	Control Group	Experimental Group
Pretest	5.13	4.87
Post test	11.37	18.90
Gained	6.23	14.03

The Study's Implications for Science Education

The preliminary results of the study showed that students' understanding of Earth Science ideas was inadequate. In response, an interactive learning module was incorporated into the study with the goal of improving student performance. The new module outperformed the

conventional one that was previously in use in terms of improving students' comprehension and performance in Earth Science.

Given that contemporary students are thought of as 21st-century learners, it seems sense that traditional teaching strategies, which primarily emphasize writing and passive reading, could hinder students' ability to advance in their academic careers. The researcher considered this when designing the interactive module in order to better meet the needs and preferences of the students throughout the learning process.

The results of the study unambiguously show how well the designed module aids in students' academic success. This research may provide a foundation for teachers who want to improve their techniques, especially when it comes to meeting the needs of students in the twenty-first century. Additionally, this research supports the incorporation of interactive teaching tools into Science instruction in line with the changing needs of contemporary schools.

Conclusion

1. The findings show that Science Experts have a high level of acceptance for the interactive learning module used to teach Earth Science in terms of content, appropriate scope, and language presentation.
2. The interactive learning module has received high marks from IT specialists for usability, functionality, and user interface, indicating that it may be implemented successfully.
3. Between the pretest and posttest, the experimental group's mean scores climbed considerably, demonstrating a notable improvement in student performance. This

shows that teaching Earth Science with the suggested module is successful.

4. The data analysis conclusion that the developed module is an effective teaching and learning tool is supported by the wide range of posttest scores obtained from the students.

5. The interactive learning module can help Earth Science teachers improve their teaching strategies and spark students' interest in the subject.

Recommendation

The study's results and findings led to the development of the following recommendations.

1. The created module is recommended for use by scientific teachers in Earth science courses; however, the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) of the Department of Education must verify it before it can be implemented.

2. Leaders in academic institutions should place a high premium on ICT integration because it is a crucial part of professional development for teachers, which aims to improve teaching techniques.

3. Furthermore, future research endeavors concerning the application of ICT in scientific education and other associated fields can draw guidance from this work.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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